

Quantum Probability and Coordinate Systems

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In previous notes, we argued that the quantum wavefunction $W(x)$ is associated with a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x)$ or quantum probability. The probabilities $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ behave as usual statistical probabilities, but $P(p/x)$ does not. It is complex and periodic leading to “interference”. Thus, it seems quantum mechanics represents a different probability scheme from that of usual probability theory. For a free quantum particle, $\exp(ipx)$ is its conditional probability and its modulus of 1 indicates equal probability $P(x)$ for each x point, yet the periodicity plus two channel $\cos(px)$, $i\sin(px)$, yields non-classical behaviour. In this note, we consider the idea of analyzing quantum probability in different coordinate systems and try to argue that interference is required in order to have consistency between the different systems. This interference seems to be identical to that which occurs by adding the wavefunctions (or quantum conditional probabilities) of “distinguishable” processes to obtain an overall wavefunction or probability.

Coordinate Systems

Two slit interference has often been considered puzzling in quantum mechanics because “probabilities which may interfere” are added for two classically distinguishable scenarios i.e. having the particle pass through one slit or another. It seems there exists a new probability scheme which allows (and possibly even requires) “interference” and describes “humping or peaks and troughs” (through interference and periodicity) usually only seen with classical waves.

We argue that this interference of conditional probability seems to already appear if one tries to describe a particular quantum behaviour using different coordinate systems. As an example, consider the free particle quantum wavefunction or conditional probability $\exp(ipz)$. This is complex and contains periodic motion, but there is no “interference”. The idea of “maximum entropy”, however, seems to be incorporated because the modulus is 1 for all z .

If $\exp(ipz)$ is expressed in spherical coordinates (1):

$$\exp(ipz) = \sum_l P_l(\theta) j_l(pr) a_l(p) (2l+1) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Where } j_l(pr) \rightarrow 1/r [\exp(i(pr-l\pi/2)) - \exp(-i(pr-l\pi/2))] \text{ when } r \rightarrow \text{infinite} \quad ((2))$$

From ((2)), the idea of maximum entropy or equal probability along r is retained in the form $\exp(ipr)$. The factor $1/r$ accounts for the radial volumes increasing with r i.e. $rr dr$ from $dx dy dz$. It is interesting that ((1)) includes interference as well as outward and inward moving spherical waves. It seems that ((1)) (which appears frequently in textbooks) is treated as a “mathematical process”, while at the same time $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ ((3)) is treated as physical in that momentum states $\exp(ipx)$ are said to be physically measurable. We argue that ((1)) should be taken as seriously as ((3)).

A main idea arising from ((1)) is that though there exists no interference in $\exp(ipz)$, it is necessary among the radial waves in order to reconstruct $\exp(ipz)$. At this point, one is dealing with probability waves and not necessarily any kind of physical wave.

Another way to consider this is to picture a quantum free particle moving with momentum p in the z direction as having its conditional probability described by a real, positive constant. On switching to spherical coordinates, one might try to retain this real, positive constant (with the addition of the $1/r$ factor for the widening of integration "boxes"), but the radial symmetry is completely different from that of linear motion in one direction. It seems that mathematically some cancellation and addition must occur, i.e. interference must occur in order to obtain one dimensional motion from the spherical coordinate scenario. In this case, there are mathematical reasons (due to different symmetries) which force "interference" to appear in the radial picture. In the two slit example, interference appears as a consequence of experimental results which seems puzzling as classically one has different interactions with the two slit potential. (In other words, classically one performs mental measurements on the particle tracking its position and motion as it moves through one slit or the other without disturbing the particle's motion in any way.)

It may be noted that in the spherical case, a complex probability is still retained as is periodicity. It seems it is periodicity which readily gives rise to interference because it allows for both positive and negative values within a cycle i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are both positive and negative. Thus, perhaps even periodicity is linked to the interference which must occur due to different coordinate systems with different symmetries describing the same result.

It is interesting to note that the spherical scenario appears to describe a much more complicated picture than $\exp(ipz)$. There are incoming and outgoing waves in addition to interference which seems unphysical when compared with $\exp(ipz)$, but is necessary to break the spherical symmetry and create the unidirectional $\exp(ipz)$. Given that one deals with probability waves and not necessarily a physical mechanism, this does not appear problematic.

Lorentz Invariance

In previous notes, we argued that $px-Et$ in the free particle conditional probability $\exp(i(px-Et))$ is a Lorentz invariant. We reiterate this here because quantum probability seems to be based on different coordinate systems and also different frames. In fact, rotations may be incorporated in Lorentz transformations. Thus, we argue that quantum probability is one which depends on different coordinates and frames which may have an important impact on the results of quantum mechanics, for example on the idea of "interference" and periodicity. It seems that in classical probability theory arguments based on different coordinates or frames are not usually made.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum conditional probability theory differs from the usual mathematical probability one in that one has complex probability which is periodic and is able to interfere. In this note, we argue that "interference" and even possibly periodicity follow if one considers different coordinate systems (which have different symmetries) or different frames. Cartesian coordinates are based on straight line basis functions, while cylindrical and spherical

coordinates, as their names imply, are based on cylindrical and spherical symmetry. Describing one dimensional motion in spherical coordinates gives rise to a very different picture (than the Cartesian one) and seems to imply that some additions and cancellations (i.e. interference) are necessary to break from a spherical to a one dimensional motion scenario.

It seems the root of quantum mechanics is based on quantum conditional probability which is very different from usual probability. Even though one may construct usual probabilities i.e. $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$, these manifest the peculiar peaks and troughs (humps) arising from the conditional probability's (periodicity and interference).

References

1. Shankar, R. Principles of Quantum Mechanics. (Plenum Press 1988) page 556